

Recommended citation: Greim, A., Taddei, F., Aumann, Q., & Müller, G. (2018). Interactive Web Apps for Visualizations in Engineering Education. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 807-814). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672704.

Interactive Web Apps for Visualizations in Engineering Education

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Conference Key Areas: Innovative Teaching and Learning Methods, Teaching Creativity & Innovation, Open and Online Engineering Education

Keywords: Visualization, Interactive Web App, Structural Mechanics, Python Bokeh

INTRODUCTION

One important part of an engineer's work is the description of the physical reality with mathematical models. This results in equations that have to be solved in order to predict the behaviour of a certain physical object. These mathematical models are a key part of today's engineering education. On the other hand, they are abstract and difficult to capture for many students, especially when the physical reality cannot be

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observed in daily live (e.g. when the calculated deflections of a bridge are very small and therefore not perceptible by humans). Therefore, visualization has always been a key issue in engineering education.

Fig. 1. Two concepts of visualizing the motion of a single-degree-of-freedom-system. The physical model on the left, the interactive web-application on the right.

At our institute this visualisation went through three historical steps:

1. Physical models (Fig.1, left) have been constructed before computers and digital projectors have been available in classrooms. The most important advantage of these models is the fact, that their behaviour shows the physical reality in a well perceptible and descriptive way, which results in a high credibility for the students. The drawbacks are their weight and dimensions, which limits the mobility on campus. Also the effort for assembly and disassembly before and after lecture can be quite high, which results in lower motivation for lecturers to use them. A small workshop for construction and maintenance of these modes at the institute is necessary. Moreover, the use of these models is limited to the lecture room. Students cannot experiment with them at home.
2. After the introduction of tablet computers, Java-based interactive applications, which had to be installed on each single lecturer's computer, have been developed and used for over one decade. Digitizing the models made the visualization more flexible and these interactive applications have been used more frequently. However, one drawback remains: The applications have not been available for the students at home, so they cannot be involved actively.
3. The last step will be presented in this paper. Fig. 1 also shows a web-based interactive application for the same purpose as the physical model in Fig. 1. It is accessible for anybody on the webpage <http://www.bm.bgu.tum.de/en/teaching/interactive-apps/>. Therefore, students can use them at home in the same manner as lecturers use them in classroom. They get actively involved in the visualization (principle three of the seven

principles in [1]). Moreover, computer applications provide – in contrast to physical models – almost unlimited possibilities of visualisation. In the shown example (Fig. 1, right), a time history plot of the deflection of the system is added.

Several studies [2-6] have shown the positive effects of interactive visualization in the learning process. Due to the fact, that programming work has to be done during development, such visualization applications have their origin in the computer science education, e.g. [3-4]. But they have also been used already in several other disciplines e.g. mechanical [5] or biomedical [6] engineering. The drawback of all cited work is, that the user always has to download either a browser plugin or has to download and execute an installation file. In some cases, students face rights restrictions in shared computers, e.g. in computer rooms at university. Moreover, these applications will not run on all operating systems (like Windows, iOS, Android, etc.) without modifications.

Up-to-date web browsers can directly execute feature-rich applications. No additional installations have to be carried out and the applications can be accessed from a smartphone, tablet, or personal computer regardless of the operating system. The initial hurdle for launching the applications is very low, which more likely leads to a frequent usage by the students.

In the following, we explain the used environment for the development of the applications and describe its capabilities using an example application. In addition, we describe methods for analysing the impact of the applications before we conclude with some lessons learnt during the development process and a summary.

1 DEVELOPMENT ENVIRONMENT FOR THE APPLICATIONS

As core element of our programming framework, we chose the open-source, Python-based library Bokeh. Bokeh is an interactive visualization library, that can be used to visualize very large or streaming data sets directly in the web browser. No additional software has to be installed by the client other than the standard web browser, so the applications can be viewed independently of the user's operating system on devices like laptops, tablets, or smartphones.

1.1 Interactivity features

The Bokeh library provides out of the box many essential components for building interactive apps, like sliders, buttons, text fields, drop-down menus, and various 2d plots, including line, bar, scatter, surface, or box plots to name but a few. Missing components can be developed with custom extensions. For example, JavaScript can be embedded using the package *NodeJS* to create a 3d plot like in Fig. 2 on the left.

One key feature of the Bokeh library is an automatic call-back, which updates the data source of the visualization periodically. For example, differential equations can be time-integrated numerically on the fly. The result for each time step can then be linked to the movement of an object.

Fig. 2. Visualisation of the sound pressure field due to diffraction at a noise barrier. *Left:* 3d plot realized using an external library. *Right:* 2d contour plot included in Bokeh (The noise barrier is the blue bar; the thin blue arrow indicates the propagation direction of the undisturbed waves.)

1.2 Publishing the Apps

To make the applications available online, a webserver with a Bokeh installation is required. The translation from Python to HTML5, which the web browser needs to display the apps, is performed directly via the Bokeh framework and as soon as the server is up and running, the apps can be accessed.

It is advisable to add a description to each application, so the students can learn about the theory behind the shown phenomena. Using JavaScript extensions, LaTeX code can be used in the description, making it very easy to present even complicated mathematical formulae. A short summary over the features of the app, e.g. which parameters can be changed, is also important. The links to all apps are collected on a landing page on our institute's website, so they can be found easily.

In this App the response due to a harmonic load is visualized. The homogenous and particular solution as well as the total solution are plotted. One can visualize that the homogenous solution is important for the initial conditions and over time its influence tends to disappear according to the damping constant.

<http://www.bm.bgu.tum.de/lehre/interactive-apps/single-degree-of-freedom-system/>

Fig. 4. This example shows how a link to an application can be included into lecture notes together with a short description.

Additional to the online distribution, links to the apps can also be included in lecture notes (Fig.4). Many students work with tablet computers, so they can click on the link

shown in the respective chapter of the lecture notes and work directly with the app, when they are studying a certain topic.

1.3 App example

In the following example, we present an app visualizing the oscillation of a single-degree-of-freedom system in order to show, how the students can interact with the app and get to know the theory behind the oscillator. Fig. 3 shows a screenshot of the app.

The app is structured in three main parts: On the left, the system with its spring, damper, and mass is shown. Below, the system properties can be modified by the user. The graphs show the deflection of the system (in time domain in the middle, in frequency domain with amplitude and phase on the right.). All presented elements are interactive. The system is animated and the plot in the middle is drawn in real time. Clicking on the buttons on the left starts, pauses, or stops the animation. Using the sliders on the bottom, all system properties like spring stiffness, damping ratio, or load-frequency ratio can be modified. All changes here have an immediate effect on the response of the system. One can observe for example that a shift of the frequency ratio to one (to the natural frequency of the system) will immediately increase the response of the system.

Fig. 3. An interactive web-app showing the behaviour of a single-degree-of-freedom system.

The app can be used during the lecture, where interesting phenomena can be shown to the students, or the students have to find parameters in order to make a certain system response visible.

1.4 Apps available so far

Up to now, we have published several applications in the field of structural mechanics and acoustics. The apps are available on the homepage of our institute

(<http://www.bm.bgu.tum.de/en/teaching/interactive-apps/>) and can be viewed and accessed by everyone. They cover the following topics:

Vector Addition	Column Buckling	Maxwell's Reciprocity
Diffraction of Sound Waves at Noise Barriers	Vibroacoustics of Plates	Discrete Fourier Transformation
Collision	Coriolis Force	Conservation of Momentum
Damped Oscillator – Free Vibration	Damped Oscillator – Forced Vibration	Pendulum (Single and Double)
Rectilinear motion	Response Spectrum Analysis (Earthquake Engineering)	Vectorial Translation

The source code of all applications is freely available on GitHub: https://github.com/ChairOfStructuralMechanicsTUM/Mechanics_Apps. A readme file with more technical details can be found there. This file shall help to reduce the initial hurdle for starting the development of own interactive web apps in the proposed environment.

2 METHODS USED FOR EVALUATION OF THE APPLICATIONS

2.1 Web Analytics

The webpage of our institute with the interactive visualization applications is continuously tracked by the web analytics tool Matomo². The following data delivered by the tool will be analysed:

- Frequency of usage of the individual applications
- Origin of the visits (country, state, town)
- Time spent using the applications

The number of visits from the town of our university can be filtered and divided by the number of students participating at our exams. This will give an impression about how often a student has used in average the applications at home.

2.2 Ordinal 5-point Likert Scale

A questionnaire will be distributed to the students at the end of the current lecture period. The following items shall be rated on an ordinal 5-point Likert scale:

- How often did you use the applications during the semester?
- Could you access the applications easily? / Did they run without problems on your computer?
- Have you been satisfied with the explanations to the applications?
- Could you control the applications intuitively?
- Did the applications allow you a better grasp of the lecture content?
- Do you expect, that you are prepared better for the examination due to the usage of the applications?

² <https://matomo.org>

Additionally, the students may leave a comment and name their favourite application.

3 FINDINGS

The applications are used for the first time during the summer semester 2018. Therefore, the evaluation and the findings based on the methods described in the previous section will be available starting from August 2018. These findings will be presented on the conference in September 2018. However, the reactions of the students after the first lectures in the current semester have been promising, some have already asked whether they can join the team of developers. In the following, we focus on some lessons learnt during the development of the applications.

4 LESSONS LEARNT

A significant programming workload is involved in the development of the interactive apps. This work has been carried out mainly by students, employed through public resources intended for improvement and digitalization in university education. The recruited students have been enrolled e.g. at the informatics department or at our faculty, in programs related to computation (e.g. Computational Mechanics or Civil Engineering with focus on computational methods). Therefore, the students have been in general keen on coding and showed a lot of creativity. They quickly familiarized with the programming environment of Python and Bokeh. On the other hand, perfectionism and endurance for consequent debugging has not been always guaranteed. Therefore, the effort for academic staff for supervising and finishing the programming work has been higher than expected. The active use of the apps in classrooms is expected to lead to improvements of interactivity and bug-findings. The latter aspect may also have a teaching function, where students can learn from errors when observing and reporting unexpected behaviours of an application.

Maintenance of the applications has to be guaranteed for the complete intended period of usage (hopefully more than one decade). The Bokeh library gets continuously improved. Therefore, objects and functions can change their input/output instructions from time to time and the interactive applications must be adapted to the technical progress.

Almost unlimited visualization methods are possible in the proposed environment, as described in 1.1. This should not prevent a developer from keeping the application simple. Students will not use an application, if it takes them too long to understand what they are expected to do with the application. Moreover, the applications shall motivate the students to play around. Therefore, immediate interaction – without reading of instructions – is important. Schweitzer and Brown [3] have already described, how important the mouse-driven interaction (e.g. with sliders and buttons) is. The developer should prevent the user from using the keyboard.

5 SUMMARY

We have proposed a development environment for interactive web-based visualization applications in engineering education. The applications are accessible from everywhere in the internet with an ordinary browser. The users do not need to perform installations on their devices. Some effort has to be put in development and maintenance, but this is in nature of things. The involvement of students in the developing process has led to several running apps and to a positive experience but

is not always a surefire success in terms of stability of the algorithms and programming optimisation. A significant effort of the academic supervisors is always necessary.

Experiences about the frequency of usage and opinions of users will be available within the next months. They will be presented on the conference.

REFERENCES

- [1] Chickering, A. W., Gamson, Z. F. (1987), Seven Principles for Good Practice in Undergraduate Education, *AAHE Bulletin*, Vol.39, No. 7n pp.3-7.
- [2] Kuosa, K. et al. (2016), Interactive Visualization Tools to Improve Learning and Teaching in Online Learning Environments, *International Journal of Distance Education Technologies (IJDET)*, Vol. 14, No.1, pp. 1-21.
- [3] Schweitzer, D., Brown W. (2007), Interactive visualization for the active learning classroom, *ACM SIGCSE Bulletin*, Vol. 39, No. 1, pp. 208-212.
- [4] Imai, Y., Moritoh, Y., Imai, M. (2014), Utilization of Java-based Web Application for Educational Visualization, *The International Conference on Education Technologies and Computers (ICETC)*, Lodz, Poland, pp. 103-109.
- [5] Goeser, P. T., Johnson, W.M., Hamza-Lup, F. G., Schaefer, D. (2011), VIEW – A Virtual Interactive Web-based Learning Environment for Engineering, *Advances in Engineering Education*, Vol. 2, No. 3.
- [6] Settapat, S., Achalakul, T., Ohkura, M. (2011), Web-Based 3D Medical Image Visualization Framework for Biomedical Engineering Education, *Computer Applications in Engineering Education*, Vol. 22, No. 2 pp. 216-226.